

THE EFFECT OF LEADER-MEMBER EXCHANGE AND ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE WITH ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE AS A MEDIATING VARIABLE (STUDY AT THE SECRETARIAT GENERAL OF THE DPR RI)

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the effect of LMX, Organizational Culture, on employee performance with Organizational Change as a Mediation Variable (Study at the Secretariat General of the DPR RI). This research used quantitative research with a causal method. The population of this study were employees in the Secretariat of the DPR RI, a total of 208 respondents. SmartPLS was used as the data analysis method. Therefore, the study results show that LMX positively and significantly affects organizational change. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on organizational change. LMX does not affect employee performance. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Organizational Changes have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. LMX has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with Organizational Change as a mediating variable. Organizational culture positively and significantly affects employee performance, with organizational change as a mediating variable.

Keywords: LMX, Organizational Culture, Organizational Change, Employee Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The developments era and trends movement, as well as the public's criticism regarding the DPR RI's poor performance (Indonesian House of Representatives of the Republic of Indonesia), trigger the Secretariat General of the DPR RI to improve. This commission is the supporting system for the DPR RI and has improved the system, work mechanism, institutional performance and human resources quality through bureaucratic reform. The DPR RI is a political institution whose performance is highly dependent on the quality of human resources in the Secretariat General commission. The management of human resources is urgently needed, especially in DPR. It is considering the unsatisfactory performance of this institution during the reform process. The people think that the DPR is an institution that can help them to solve their problems, but in reality, the people see the opposite. Indeed, it results in dissatisfaction.

In supporting the implementation of the powers and duties of the DPR RI, a Secretariat General was formed as stated in Presidential Regulation Number 26 of 2020 by the Secretariat General of the DPR RI. Based on Presidential Regulation Number 26 of 2020 article 3, the Secretariat General of the DPR is the secretariat of an upper house with the main task of

providing technical, administrative, and expert services to the Leaders and Members of the DPR. State Civil Apparatus (ASN) who work in the Secretariat General have unique duties and functions because they are not directly involved in public services. They serve members of the Council that will directly impact the community through produced law, through the control over the implementation of laws by the government and in prudence state budget plan. In improving employee performance, the Secretariat General of the DPR RI has made improvements that the government has determined through bureaucratic reform. It includes changing the organizational structure in 2021, the legal basis for Regulation of the Secretary General of the DPR Number 6 of 2021 concerning Organization and Work Procedures of the Secretary General of DPR RI. This structural change was carried out to support the Secretariat General in achieving good governance.

2. THEORETICAL REVIEW

Performance

Mangkunegara (2015: 67) states that performance is defined as the quality and quantity of work result that an employee (State Civil Apparatus) in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. Robbins (2008) also defines that performance can result from individual or group work within an organization.

Performance is a measure of the success of an organization. A good performance will produce a good work achievement. Performance is formally defined as the value of a set of expert behaviors that contribute, either positively or negatively, to achieving organizational goals. The definition of performance includes an act that controls the expert. However, it has a limit that is relevant (or not) to the performance. Performance is the desired result of behaviour, so the performance can reflect the results of work that have a strong relationship with the organization's strategic goals and produce a positive contribution. This performance is a benchmark for the success of an organization; with good performance, the work targets will be achieved. Performance is the willingness of a person or people to carry out an activity and do it perfectly, following their responsibilities to achieve job satisfaction. Performance in carrying out its functions does not stand alone but is related to job satisfaction and the level of rewards, influenced by skills, abilities and individual characteristics.

An organization is formed to achieve organizational goals. The achievement of organizational goals shows the results of work/achievements and organizational performance. The work results are obtained from a series of activities carried out. These activities can be managing organizational resources or implementing work processes to achieve organizational goals. Ensuring these activities can achieve the expected results, management efforts are needed to manage the activities of the State Civil Apparatus.

ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE

Robbins (2014: 217) in Rahardian (2013, 18) state that organizational change is moving an organizational condition from current to future conditions as planned to increase the work effectiveness of the State Civil Apparatus. Robbin and Conter (2012:4) argue that

organizational change includes any change related to people, structure or technology. Organizational change is the effort of the community in the organization, working together to achieve a common goal by making changes in various aspects. It also means adjusting to the era's development. It used to achieve its goals and survive in the era of great change.

Change is a very powerful force which can motivate or demotivate. The change means leaving something old for something new. The changes can be done after considering the urgency in the organization Brian Clegg (2013:31) in Debrike Shiskia (2017: 2860). The changes in the organizational environment in business strongly influence the organization. Every change that occurs will always impact every aspect of the organization, such as value-added results, complex structure, the span of control, management, work groups, work structure, activity processes and communication or delegation Isniar et al., (2018:55).

Every change affects not only one structural or cultural aspect as a variable that must be changed but also both aspects must be managed together to gain an optimal result. However, in practice, the decision-makers tend only to pay attention to structural changes because the results of these changes can be felt directly. Meanwhile, cultural changes are often left behind because the results of these changes are invincible. Managing organizational change increases the ability to face challenges and opportunities. It means that organizational change must be directed at changing human behaviour and organizational processes. So, the organizational movement has become more effective in forming a more adaptive and flexible organization.

ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE

According to Mangkunegara (2014), the organizational culture is a set of assumptions or belief systems, values, and norms developed in organizations that serve as behavioural guidelines for members to address external and internal adaptation problems. Then, according to Rivai and Mulyadi (2012), organizational culture is a framework that guides daily behaviour, makes decisions for employees, and directs their actions to achieve organizational goals. Organizational culture is a pattern of organizational beliefs and values understood, inspired, and practised by the organization so that the pattern gives its meaning and becomes the basic guidelines to behave in the organization. Therefore, organizational culture is used as a controller and direction in shaping human attitudes and behaviour in the organization. Organizational culture is expected to positively influence the organizational members and the organization, especially in achieving the vision, mission, and organizational goals. Organizational culture can be defined as a system of values, beliefs, assumptions or norms that have long been applied, agreed upon and followed by members of an organization as behavioural guidelines and solving organizational problems (Darodjat 2015). Indeed, the theories above explain that organization is a concept that grows continuously and must be considered in an organization to create a good culture within the company.

LEADER-MEMBER EXCHANGE

Leaders must pay attention to the relationship quality between leaders and employees. The theory that regulates the relationship between leaders and employees is called the Leader-Member Exchange (LMX). According to Graen and Uhl-Bien (1995), LMX is based on the

reciprocal relationship between employees and leaders. LMX is considered a social exchange of trust, ideas and obligations. In addition, Liden and Maslyn (1998) stated that act-related behaviours, respect for leaders' skills and knowledge, loyalty to one another, and liking for others could contribute to the development of LMX. In its application, the Leader-Member Exchange leadership system can generate feedback between individuals without being affected by social boundaries. Leaders and employees can communicate regardless of seniority and position. It can have a positive impact on the company. LMX theory differs from most other leadership theories, which assume that leaders behave similarly towards each of their subordinates. LMX focuses on discussing the relationship between leaders and subordinates independently rather than the relationship between leaders and subordinates as a whole, where there are differences in the quality of relationships between different individuals (in Lunenburg, FC, 2010). Good LMX quality is characterized by mutual support between leaders and subordinates, mutual trust, good and comfortable communication, loyalty to others and good interpersonal attractiveness. In contrast, low LMX quality is characterized by limited mutual influence and support between leaders. And subordinates. Leaders also impose formal authority and provide benefits only to organizational standards toward their subordinates (Deluga, R. J, 1998).

Figure 1. Framework

HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

The Influence of Leader-Member Exchange on Organizational change

H1: leader-member exchange has a positive and significant effect on organizational change

To pursue organizational goals, there need to be leaders in an organization. Leadership is closely related to change. Leaders determine the organization's direction by developing a vision of the future, and then they unify the people by communicating this vision and inspiring them to overcome obstacles. LMX focuses on the dyadic (two-way) relationship between the leader and each of his subordinates which is an exchange relationship that can increase the organization's success by creating a positive relationship between the leader and his subordinates. Besides the LMX, there is an organizational culture that also influences the performance of employees. Cultural similarities between the organization and its members

will generate a sense of workplace comfort. The cultural similarities also comfort and relax their subordinates in doing their respective duties. Therefore, organizations need to build a culture that aligns with the organization's needs.

H2: Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on organizational change

The organizational changes include the changes in structure, technology application, and application of HRM that can influence the organizational culture. Organizational culture exerts a great deal of influence on individuals and organizational processes. Culture directs the individuals to act in certain directions and think and act consistently with the organization's culture. No single best type of organizational culture can be universally applicable. The most important thing is that the organization must know the current portrait of the organizational culture and evaluate whether the prevailing culture can support the organizational movement. The high involvement of organizational members will ensure the success of efforts to build a new organizational culture to support organizational change.

Prior research using indicators of organizational culture conducted by Iljin et al. (2015) found that organizational culture significantly impacts the organizational atmosphere.

H3: the leader-member exchange has a positive and significant effect on employee performance

The relationship with the leader becomes a factor that affects employee performance. If the employee has a bad relationship with the leader, the employee tends to do an ideal work, affecting the company. In addition, the relationship with the leader and the relationship between co-workers is also important because performance is the ability of a person or group to fulfil responsibilities. A good perception of LMX can improve employees' performance; a good relationship with the leadership results in smooth communication between employees and leaders. With the communication that has been established, employees can exchange ideas with their leaders regarding the organization.

It is supported by research conducted by Tariq et al. (2014) about the impact of leader-member exchange on organizational performance and commitment to organizational culture as moderators: a non-monetary tactic to enhance outcome.

H4: Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance

A relationship between organizational culture and the employees' or members' performance can be reflected in the organization's behaviour. When employees imitate behaviour that follows their organizational culture, there will be satisfaction and even direct or indirect rewards. Organizational culture becomes a basic behaviour for its members, who are unconsciously applied in each activity. A relationship between organizational culture and the performance of employees or members of the organization can be reflected in the organization's behaviour. When employees adjust their behaviour to their organizational culture, satisfaction and direct or indirect rewards will be satisfied. Organizational culture becomes a basic guideline for its members who are unconsciously applied in their activities.

The prior research by Santosa (2016) stated that organizational culture has a positive and

significant effect on employee performance.

H5: Organizational change has a positive and significant impact on employee performance

Organizational changes are followed by changes in structure, organizational goals, technology and, at the same time, changes in the work environment. The rapid technological developments trigger employees to improve their abilities to keep pace with technological developments. These changes require the employee to upgrade their skills or knowledge. These changes will affect employee performance. The purpose of organizational change is to find new ways that are improved by using existing resources to improve the organization's quality, effectiveness and accountability to its stakeholders. It means that changes made in the organization cannot be separated from efforts to improve employee performance from past circumstances.

Research conducted by Puloakan (2016) found that organizational change has a positive effect on employee performance.

H6: Organizational change takes a role in mediating the effect of LMX on employee performance

Leaders must pay attention to the relationship quality between leaders and employees. The theory that regulates the relationship between leaders and employees is called the Leader-Member Exchange (LMX). According to Graen and Uhl-Bien (1995), LMX is based on the reciprocal relationship between employees and leaders. LMX is considered a social exchange of trust, ideas and obligations. In addition, Liden and Maslyn (1998) stated that work-related behaviours, respect for leaders' skills and knowledge, loyalty to one another, and liking for one another could contribute to the development of LMX. The leader-member exchange leadership system can generate feedback between individuals without being affected by boundaries or social strata. Leaders and employees can communicate regardless of seniority and position so that it can have a positive impact on the company. In line with previous research conducted by Arif et al. (2017) showed a positive and significant influence of leader-member exchange on employee performance.

H7: Organizational change takes a role in mediating the influence of organizational culture on employee performance

The change management system will lead to the adaptability and flexibility of HR to adapt their work in line with the demands of the company's external environment. It will lead to improvement the performance. Organizations must learn to change and adjust in every situation. The change is underlined just for the organization that allows flexibility, freedom of innovation, and proactive culture. It does not only improve the organizational performance but also individuals so that employees are accustomed to and able to take on greater responsibilities in the future

Prior research conducted by Iljin et al. (2015) found that organizational culture has a significant impact on organizational climate

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study aims to determine the effect of Leader-Member Exchange Behavior and organizational culture on employee performance with organizational change as a mediating variable. In this study, data were obtained by distributing questionnaires to 208 respondents who were employees of the Secretariat General of the DPR RI, which became the pilot unit for the integrity zone.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

This stage is carried out to determine whether the research hypothesis proposed in the research model is accepted or rejected. In testing the proposed hypothesis, it can be seen from the path coefficients, the T-Statistic value through the bootstrapping procedure and the p-value.

Table 1. Path Coefficient Values

			Original Sample (O)	Mean Sample (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T-Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
PERFORMANCE ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE	OF	->	0.279	0.282	0.082	3.391	0.001
ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE	OF	->	0.423	0.418	0.072	5.909	0.000
LMX -> PERFORMANCE			0.073	0.067	0.082	0.886	0.376
LMX ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE	OF	->	0.322	0.328	0.069	4.676	0.000
PERFORMANCE ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE	OF	->	0.391	0.396	0.064	6.145	0.000

Source: data process 2022

Based on the result table of hypothesis testing about the influence of variable independent toward dependent variable, it can be concluded that:

1. H1: Leader-Member Exchange has a significant effect on Organizational Change

Based on the test results on the influence of the Leader-Member Exchange on Organizational Change, the result is that the path coefficients value is 0.322, the T-Statistic value is 4.676 (>1.96), and the P-value is 0.000 (<0.05), then H1 is accepted. Leader-Member Exchange has a Positive and Significant Influence on organizational change.

2. H2: Organizational Culture Has Significant Effect on Organizational Change

Based on the test results of Organizational Culture on Organizational Change influence, it results in a path coefficient value of 0.423, a T-Statistic value of 5.909 (>1.96) and a P-value of 0.000 (<0.05), then H2 is accepted. Organizational Culture Positive and Significant Influence on organizational change.

3. H3: Leader-Member Exchange Affects employee performance

Based on the test results on the Influence of Leader-Member Exchange on Performance, the results of the path coefficients value is 0.073, the T-Statistic value is 0.886 (<1.96), and the P-Value is 0.376 (>0.05), then H3 is rejected. Leader-Member Exchange has a positive but not significant effect on performance.

4. H4: Organizational Culture Significantly Affects Employee Performance

Based on the test results on the influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance, it has a path coefficient value of 0.279, a T-Statistic value of 3.391 (>1.96) and a P-value of 0.001 (<0.05), then H4 is accepted. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

5. H5: Organizational Change Significantly Affects Employee Performance

Based on the test results on the influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance, it shows that the path coefficients value is 0.391, the T-Statistic value is 6.145 (>1.96), and the P-value is 0.000 (<0.05), then H5 is accepted. Organizational Changes Have a Positive and Significant Effect on Employee Performance.

6. H6: Leader-Member Exchange positively and significantly impacts employee performance with organizational changes as a mediating variable.

The mediating variable is based on the test results on the indirect effect of the Leader-Member Exchange and Employee Performance. The results of organizational change have a path coefficient value of 0.165, a T-Statistic value of 4.096 (>1.96) and a P-Value of 0.000 (>0.05), so it can be concluded that the hypothesis H6 is accepted. Then, the leader-member exchange has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with organizational change as a mediating variable

7. H6: Organizational Culture Has a Positive and Significant Effect on Employee Performance with Organizational Changes as a mediating variable.

Based on the test results on the indirect effect of Culture and Employee Performance through the mediating variable, organizational change. It results in a path coefficient value

of 0.126, a T-Statistic value of 3.973 (>1.96) and a P-Value of 0.000 (>0.05), so it can be concluded that hypothesis H7 Accepted and Organizational Culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with organizational change as a mediating variable.

Table 2. Test Results of Indirect Effects of Independent Variables on Dependent Variables

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P-Values
ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE -> ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE CHANGE	0.165	0.166	0.040	4.096	0.000
LMX CHANGE -> ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE	0.126	0.129	0.032	3.973	0.000

Source: data process 2022

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Leader-Member Exchange on Organizational Change

This Leader-Member Exchange Theory will indirectly have a positive impact on employees. It will make employees ready for change or readiness to change. So, employees will approve, implement and fully support any organizational changes.

The research conducted by Arif et al. (2016) found that leader-member exchange positively and significantly influences organizational change.

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Organizational Change

This research is new. No journal or prior research has been found that explains the presence or absence of the influence of organizational culture on organizational change. It can be a science or a new phenomenon requiring further research on organizational culture and organizational change.

The Influence of Leader-Member Exchange on Employee Performance

The test results show no significant effect between the Leader-Member Exchange and the performance of ASN at the Secretariat General of the DPR RI. It means that the level of influence of LMX felt by ASN cannot affect the performance of ASN at the Secretariat General. LMX is a form of interaction between leaders and subordinates. This relationship

can be developed through employees' leadership, and vice versa of exchange relationships can be developed by subordinates and perceived by superiors. A high-quality relationship will occur and produce interdependence, loyalty and supportive condition. So the employees can work calmly and result in high performance. Due to the absence of a significant influence from the Leader-member Exchange on the performance of ASN, organizations can look for other indicators that can improve employee performance, such as improving work culture.

It is also in line with research conducted by Zulfa (2021), which suggests that LMX has no significant effect on employee performance at PT Berlian Jasa Terminal Indonesia.

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance

The organizational culture creates a common understanding among employees about how big the organization is and how employees should behave. It means that organizational culture can equalize perceptions and behaviours to suit the company's vision. The company or organization's reputation can be seen from the behaviour and performance of its employees (Utami et al., 2017). Sagita et al. (2018) stated in their journal that a good organizational culture could significantly improve employee performance. Another study that strengthens this theory is the research of Ismail (2017), which proves that organizational culture affects employee performance positively.

The Effect of Organizational Changes on Employee Performance

The results of this study indicate that organizational change significantly affects employee performance at the Secretariat General of the DPR RI. It means that organizational change becomes very important and is needed to improve the performance of employees. It shows that organizational changes carried out by the Secretariat General of the DPR RI positively influence each employee's performance, especially in the increased work given. Organizations must adjust to the development of technology and information to achieve organizational goals economically. Organizations that are unable to adapt become stagnate. They are not strong enough to compete with other companies because they lack the organization's quality and quantity. Increasing organizational effectiveness to improve the organizational competence in adapting to environmental changes and the organizational members' attitudes is the basis for the company's purpose of making changes (Robbins and Judge, 2015:413). Organizations must consider factors affecting employee performance, one of which is organizational change. Organizations must understand how organizational changes can impact performance because environmental changes are unavoidable (Wanza and Nkuraru, 2016).

It is supported by Poluakan's research (2016) that examines the Effect of Organizational Change and Development on Employee Performance at PT. Sinar Galesong Prima Manado. This research results have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. An organization can only survive if it can adjust to every change. In line with previous research conducted by Jansen (2019), the effect of organizational change can be seen in the quantity of output, output period, attendance at work and cooperative attitude in dealing with any organizational changes set by the company.

The Influence of Leader-Member Exchange on Employee Performance with Organizational Change as a Mediation Variable.

Increasing LMX can increase employee commitment to the organization. Leader-member exchange has a direct effect on organizational commitment. LMX is a form of interaction between leaders and subordinates. This relationship can be developed through the leaders to its employees and vice versa. The exchange relationships can be developed by subordinates and perceived by superiors. A high-quality relationship will occur in a condition that allows for interdependence, loyalty and support so that employees can work calmly and produce high performance. The relationship will increase if the organizational change is committed and directed. It can result in the influence of LMX on performance becoming higher than before.

The Organizational Culture against Employee Performance with Organizational Change as a Mediation Variable.

Organizational change variables have a positive and significant effect on employee performance variables. It means that the changes in employee performance are largely determined by the success or failure of the changes. Organizational change requires employees to add new skills and knowledge to the changes. One of the vital prospects in organizational change is the formation of an organizational culture that follows the direction and objectives of bureaucratic reform to lead to changes in employee attitudes and work performance. The changes in the organization increase the effectiveness of the organization. It can lead to changes in the environment and the actions of people in the organization. Prior research conducted by Utami et al. (2017) show the significant effect of organizational change on employee performance at PT Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk at the Solo Branch Office. It means that if the company increase organizational changes, it can improve employee performance.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Based on the research findings and the discussion, the researcher has answered all the research problems described previously in this study. From the analysis that has been carried out, it can conclude that:

1. The Leader-Member Exchange has a positive and significant effect on organizational change at the Secretariat General of the DPR RI.
2. Organizational culture positively and significantly affects organizational change in the Secretariat General of the DPR RI.
3. Leader-Member Exchange has no significant effect on employee performance at the Secretariat General of the DPR RI.
4. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Secretariat General of the DPR RI

5. Organizational changes have a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees at the Secretariat General of the DPR RI.
6. Leader-member exchange has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with organizational change as a mediating variable at the Secretariat General of the DPR RI.
7. Organizational culture positively and significantly affects employee performance, with organizational change mediating variable at the Secretariat General of the DPR RI.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Managerial Advice

1. For leaders, in relation to the Leader-Member Exchange, leaders at the Secretariat General of the DPR RI should appreciate the potential that employees possess. It is used to create high employee performance.
2. Organizational changes directly impact employee performance, so the Secretariat General of the DPR RI must pay attention to these changes. The more organizational changes are improved by the Secretariat General of the DPR RI, the more employees' performance at the Secretariat General of the DPR RI. In this study, the span of control value is the highest value for the indicator of organizational change. It means that the span of management affects the efficiency of managers and the effective performance of their subordinates. The wide span can mean managers have to control many subordinates, causing inefficiency. At the same time, a span of control that is too narrow can result in managers not being fully utilized.
3. Organizational culture is an indicator with the highest value in measuring employee performance. Employees work to make a positive contribution. In this case, the work culture becomes a kind of bond that guides every group in the organization to move in the broader direction. Then the stronger the values that all employees share in all organizations result, the better performance of the organization. It is due to the organization's more efficient use of human resources.
4. Teamwork is needed between teams in carrying out their respective tasks to achieve good employee performance. Good work result often comes not only from your abilities but also because of co-workers' support. Teamwork is important because no one can work alone, especially in a company/organization

FURTHER RESEARCH SUGGESTIONS

After conducting research with several limitations, the author has several suggestions for further research, including:

1. Analyze employee performance more deeply and broadly, focusing on one type of model and with various modifications to the research model based on the existing literature

or journals so that the results obtained are even better.

2. Researchers suggest that researchers conduct further research on factors outside the variables studied, such as employee satisfaction, leadership, turnover and teamwork.

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